

THE WAYS OF CONSTRUCTING ITEMS IN READING TESTS

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ABSTRACT

In this article ways of constructing items in reading tests are demonstrated. The investigation of the effect of item test characteristics on the difficulty of reading comprehension item often involves an analysis of various variables including passage features, question type features and question format variables. The study is based on describing the process of developing an academic reading ability test undertaken as a class project and to evaluate its authenticity. The basic purpose of the test is to develop the ability of designing and developing a language test of the students of a class of English language teaching. Thus, in this way along with the learning of the principles of language testing and assessment, the students have also been given a practical experience of designing and developing a test.

Broadly speaking, the purpose of educational testing and assessment is straightforward; to measure or gauge what learners know or can do. Testing or assessment is seen as a process of gathering evidence to infer the performance of an individual (McNamara, 2000). In the educational context, many educators recognize that tests play a crucial role as an arsenal of tools to measure student achievement. The results of standardized tests serve a variety of purposes in educational settings. At the individual level, Mertler (2007) asserts that test scores are used to describe one's learning abilities and levels of achievements. The information helps students to identify their areas of strength

and weakness (Schwartz, 1984) and this guides them to modify or adapt to the instruction based on their own needs (Mertler, 2007). In addition, test results can provide useful information at group level. Often, test results are used to compare students with other students (Schwartz, 1984). Tests serve as an indicator of general ability levels of students across classes, grade levels, schools or states.

It is clear that a construction of reading assessment requires a series of decisions. It is a demanding task for test writers to decide what skills to measure, how to measure them and how to interpret the test score. Despite its challenges, it has been acknowledged that assessment of

reading plays a crucial role in educational practice and research. It is claimed that reading test results can be used as an indicator for evaluation of various approaches to the teaching of reading (Pumfrey, 1976; Schwartz, 1984) and for improvement of reading comprehension ability (Snow, 2003). This is because of the positive washback⁴ of reading assessment that provides strategies for researchers and teachers to identify and diagnose reading comprehension problem in students. The importance of reading assessment then justifies that research on comprehension assessment is paramount. In his introductory note of Alderson's (2000) book, Bachman recognized that "reading, through which we can access worlds of ideas and feelings, as well as the knowledge of the ages and visions of the future, is at once the most extensively researched and the most enigmatic of the so-called language skills"

In the field of language testing, it has been identified that the performance of students on a comprehension test is a result of interaction between reader, text and test. Bachman and Palmer (1996) highlighted that the characteristics of the tasks and the characteristics of individuals that affect both language use and language test performance should be of central interest in designing any language test. Alderson (2000) also agreed that characteristics of both reader and test will affect the reading assessment. Based on the correspondence between reader, text and test, one of the main concerns in reading comprehension research has been the estimation of the contribution of the characteristics of test features that are related or unrelated to the construct being measured and/or test takers to the

performance of reading ability. Moreover, the identification of those factors is a prime concern in language testing to achieve a construct validation result (Bachman, 1990; McNamara, 1996). This is to ensure that the test is not affected by threats which may influence the performance of the students.

Acknowledging the importance of the dynamic interaction between reader, text and test, the present study aims to identify the test features and individual characteristics that contribute to the item difficulty of the MUET reading comprehension. For the first part of the study, several test features have been identified to investigate the effect of these characteristics on item difficulty. The second part of the study comprises a statistical analysis of test item: differential item functioning (DIF) in order to understand the relationship between students' characteristics and test items.

The investigation of the effect of item test characteristics on the difficulty of reading comprehension item often involves an analysis of various variables including passage features, question type features and question format variables.

Therefore, it is important here to differentiate the variables under consideration into two subgroups: construct-relevant and construct-irrelevant variance. Alderson (2000) has asserted that constructs of reading are those "variables that have an impact on either the reading process or its products" (p. 120). He further exemplifies those factors such as text variables, linguistic features, reader's background, subject/topic knowledge and a range of relevant reading skills and strategies as important components of reading constructs. It is

obvious that the first two variables passage features and question type features which are included as the constructs of reading.

On the other hand, construct-irrelevant variance refers to the situation where a test gauges proficiencies irrelevant to the intended construct. Alderson (2000) identified that overemphasis on metacognition and metalinguistic knowledge, as well as readers' motivation and emotional state, are likely to underrepresent the construct of reading. He also has explicitly highlighted that the test method is one of the sources that can contaminate the constructs of reading assessment. Evidently, the last variable used in this study – question format – is a source of construct-irrelevant variance.

Passage Feature Variables

Several features of text have been investigated to predict the difficulty of the reading test. The most typical variable for passage feature is *the type of the text*. In the Progressive Achievement Test in Reading (known as PAT-R), a reading comprehension test used in Australian Schools, five text types are used; narrative, factual, expository, tabular or graphical and procedural (Stephanou, Anderson & Urbach, 2008). In other research regarding the type of text, Carr (2006) classified passage variables into arts, humanities, social science, life science and earth/physical science. He also divided passage variables into rhetorical features, propositional content, cohesion and focus constructions. Another commonly used text feature is *the length of the passage*. This feature is coded according to the number of paragraphs and lines each passage contains (Scheuneman & Gerritz, 1990). It is assumed that passages with more sentences or words are potentially

more difficult to comprehend.

Other studies have indicated a growing interest in examining other new features of passage variable known to affect reading comprehension, including propositional density of the text (Ozuru, Rowe, O'Reilly & McNamara, 2008) word frequency (Ozuru *et al.*, 2008; Davey, 1988; Scheuneman & Gerritz, 1990, Drum, Calfee & Cook, 1981), concreteness (Davey, 1988) and proportion of clauses (Davey, 1988).

Question Type Variables

Researchers have used a variety of categories for the classification of question type. Generally, the assumed level of cognitive operation provided by Bloom taxonomies has dominated most of the question type in reading test and other language tests as well (Davey, 1988; Davey & Macready, 1985, McKenna & Stahl, 2009). These questions range from items requiring simple retrieval of information in the passage to those involving higher level of inference and reasoning.

Pearson and Johnson (1978), classified question type into three simpler taxonomies: *textually explicit*, *textually implicit* and *script-based* (Alderson, 2000; Davey, 1988). Textually explicit questions are those items having both the question information and the correct answer in a single sentence. Textually implicit questions, on the other hand, require the examinee to locate the information across sentences. The third category, script-based, involves the integration of text information and reader's background knowledge and the correct answer cannot be found in the text itself.

The coding scheme above is somewhat similar to McKenna and Stahl's (2009) three levels of question types: 1) *Literal questions* involve retrieval of information

that has been explicitly mentioned in the text, 2) *Inferential questions* require readers to make logical connections among the facts in the text in order to arrive at an answer which cannot be located in the passage, and 3) *Critical questions* call for value judgement about the reading material and definitely the answers are not in the text. Using the same framework of cognitive operation in locating the answers and making inference, PAT-R has grouped the items of reading comprehension into: *retrieving directly stated information (RI)*, *reflecting on texts (RF)*, *interpreting explicit information (IF)* and *interpreting by making inferences (II)* (Stephanou *et al.*, 2008). In addition to the previously mentioned categories, McKay (2006) added another type known as *textbased questions* that focus on the grammatical and vocabulary knowledge of the readers. Another way of categorizing question type is to distinguish between abstract and concrete information requested by a question. Mosenthal (1996) addressed the level of abstractness or concreteness of the information in a question and coded the items into five levels: 1) *the most concrete* - calls for identification of persons, animals, or things, 2) *highly concrete* - asks for information about time, attributes or amounts, 3) *intermediate* - requires the identification of manner, goal, purpose, alternative, attempt or condition, 4) *highly abstract* - involves the identification of cause, effect, reason or result, and 5) *the most abstract* - calls for information on equivalence, difference or theme.

Other classifications of question type have been suggested by other researchers to predict the difficulty of reading comprehension items. Researchers have begun to use the question-classification

framework of prior studies and suggested their own version of coding schemes (e.g. Ozuru *et al.*, 2007, 2008; Scheuneman & Gerritz, 1990; Davey, 1988).

Question Format Variables

Perhaps the most popular classification of question format in reading tests is the *multiple-choice item vs. free-response item*. Several works have demonstrated that question formats can serve as a source of difficulty of reading comprehension items (e.g. Davey, LaSasso & Macready, 1983; Ebel, 1982).

Due to the fact that standardized reading tests often utilize the multiple-choice format, classifications of question format focus on features of multiple-choice items which consist of stem and alternatives (made up of several wrong answers, known as distractors, and at least one correct answer). For example, stem, the stimulus segment or statement of a multiple-choice item, is frequently grouped into *wh- direct question*⁸ and *incomplete statement*⁹ format (Popham, 2000).

Other question format variables that have become of interest for exploration include stem length, stem content words, structure of alternatives/options, length of correct answer and distractors, etc. For example, Scheuneman and Gerritz (1990) recommended three categories of option structures based on the previous work of Carlton and Harris (1989). The categories were: a) *complete sentence or complex phrases containing clauses that could stand alone as sentence*, b) *simple phrases*, and c) *short lists of 1-4 words*. In another study, question format is addressed in terms of the falsity of the distractors. A *falsifiable distractor* means that the information which establishes that the option is incorrect is explicit in the text, whereas a

distractor is not falsifiable if the passage does not provide explicit textual evidence (Ozuru *et al.*, 2008).

According to Bachman's and Palmer's (1996) philosophy of language testing, fairness is one of the central considerations in test design. Fairness stipulates equal educational opportunities for all students regardless of their ethnic background, economic and social status and gender. The Code of Fair Testing in Education developed by the Joint Committee on Testing Practices (2004) urges test developers to design tests that are as fair as possible without demeaning the examinees of different races, ethnic background, gender or demographical location (rural and urban). Fairness is a complex and broad area, involving test design, development, test administration and scoring procedures (Kunnan, 2000; Popham, 2000; McNamara & Roever, 2006). In the layperson's view, bias is typically associated with unfairness and favouritism. Psychometrically, Angoff (1993) defined an item is biased if test takers of equal ability from different groups respond differently to the item. Shepard *et al.* (1981) defined bias as "a kind of invalidity that harms one group than another" (p. 318). In the language testing context, examination items are considered biased if they contain sources of difficulty that are not relevant to the construct being measured (Zumbo, 1999).

This suggests that bias is present when construct-irrelevant characteristics of the test takers influence the score of a test. An item might also be considered biased if it contains language or content that is differentially difficult for different subgroups of test-takers. In addition, an item might demonstrate item structure and

format bias if there are ambiguities or inadequacies in the item stem, test instructions, or distracters (Hambleton & Rogers, 1995). There are two methods to investigate potential bias in measurement/assessment (Zumbo, 1999); (a) judgmental and (b) statistical. Zumbo recommended that in a highstake test, statistical techniques seem feasible and defensible to flag potentially biased items and this leads us to differential item functioning (DIF). The problem of inconsistent behaviour of common items across administrations can be viewed as an instance of (DIF), where two groups taking two different forms with some items in common are the focal and reference groups.

The study is based on describing the process of developing an academic reading ability test undertaken as a class project and to evaluate its authenticity. The study is of multidimensional nature and consists of the following steps:

- ☑ Discussing the purpose of the test and the construct that underlies it.
- ☑ Describing the process of test development in relation to test validation.
- ☑ Evaluating the draft test on the basis of the results of the trial.

The basic purpose of the test is to develop the ability of designing and developing a language test of the students of a class of English language teaching. Thus, in this way along with the learning of the principles of language testing and assessment, the students have also been given a practical experience of designing and developing a test. Now we discuss the test in relation to the three steps mentioned above.

A test's specifications tell us about what the test tests and how it tests it. "Test

specifications are the blueprint to be followed by test and item writers, and they are also essential in the establishment of the test's construct validity." (Alderson et al., 1995, p. 9). The test is based on assessing proficiency in reading skill which involves the ability of drawing meaning from a text and interpreting the information appropriately (Grabe and Stoller, 2002). The test was designed for

the tertiary level learners of English enrolled in Foundation Certificate in English for Academic Purpose (FCertEAP) at English Language Academy (ELA), a language centre of the University of Auckland where various English language courses are conducted for foreign learners.

taqdiriga befarq bo'lmagan har bir ota-ona jiddiy e'tibor bilan qarashi zarur.

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